

AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
CROP DISEASE DETECTION SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT
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Date: 2026/02/02

Abstract

Farmers find difficulties in identifying and detecting as well as treating the plant diseases and its cause. And Fruits are more prone to diseases depending on the season and environmental conditions they grow during cultivation also they get more infections. The early and traditional method of predicting the disease in fruits and plants is very difficult. Using the proposed model one can make a huge dataset of different types of fruits and its diseases with huge number of images stored in different folders for processing the data set. Each data set Is categorized with type of disease and fruit. This system is trained and tested easily Artificial Neural Networking is used to learn and classify categorize the fruits and diseases. Proposed model can detect accurate disease and get preventive measures and some suggestions to the farmers. This system will benefit the farmers across the world.

Introduction

Fruits are vulnerable to infections during the period of their cultivation. The factors favoring such diseases is unknown to the farmers either, this cause the decrease in the production of fruits. The application accommodates a variety of plant categories in its learned model to identify from. The user can scan the suspicious plant for disease identification from the application camera. The goal of such an application is to facilitate expert decision on the plant health as per specified by the botanical community. It is a dire task to identify plant diseases for the uneducated farmers in real life. A brief description of each disease is mentioned, along with a reasonable solution and all the help needed. The application has the option of adding new learned models on different plants or new disease developed with the help of botanist or any other agriculture or plantation associations.

The main cause for the fruit disease is virus or the bacteria's. Application includes identifying the diseases in fruit that cause loss in production and quality showed up in reaping. Distinguishing and grouping of diseases of fruit is important to recognize what are the control factors must be taken one year from now to stay away from losses in the production. Fruit types and their respective disease are as follows.

- **Apple**

Apple fruits are susceptible for number of viral and bacterial diseases, namingly

- a. Apple Scab
- b. Black Rot Canker
- c. Powdery mildew
- d. Sooty blotch and fly speck

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

- **Banana**

The disease attacks banana plants at all phases of development. Few of the disease that attacks banana are as follows

- a. Moko Disease
- b. Crown Rot
- c. Cigar End Tip

(a)

(b)

(c)

- **Mango**

Mango fruit is vulnerable to many disease since it has specific season and farmers keep high hope on this cultivation but some of disease make burden to farmers the diseases are

- a. Anthracnose
- b. Die Back
- c. Phoma Blight
- d. Bacterial Canker

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

The proposed model uses CNN algorithm, technically CNN works on model train and test the application main works with TensorFlow and Mobile net as well mobilnet in cnn is a efficient and portable CNN architecture.

Model is basically consists steps like training the huge datasets with different type of diseases of different fruits and then testing them with input image, algorithm follows many steps like image acquisition, assigning importance, weights and biases to various objects in the image.

Background

The main goal of this dissertation is to develop a system to enable farmers to accurately identify different crop diseases using images taken from smartphone cameras. Over recent years deep learning has proven to offer great opportunities for image classification and object recognition capabilities[5].

It involves training a neural network using a dataset of images collected from actual crop leaves affected by a disease[6]. After the model has been trained it can be integrated into a mobile application or deployed on a cloud server for use as a crop disease detector.

Traditional computer vision was mainly based on image processing algorithms and methods. It was mainly used for extracting the features of the image which includes detecting the corners, edges, and color of objects. The main challenge with this approach used in traditional computer vision for a classification task is that you must choose which features to look for in each given image.

It becomes hard to cope up when the number of features of classes becomes high. The introduction of deep learning DL has pushed the limits of what was possible in image classification. There is no longer need of manually choosing the features. Simply put if you want a deep learning network to classify objects, you do not explicitly tell it which features to look for in an image. You just show it thousands of images and it will train itself to classify the given images for you without writing any code.

Motivation of Work

We have explored many researches done on image processing and machine learning in agriculture domain. Machine learning techniques such as neural network, CNN are applied for different purpose such as classification; feature extraction etc. even this kind of research is helpful to Farmer, Agriculture based system, Bio farm and researcher. After all observation we have decided to work on orange fruit diseases detection and which disease using Image Processing and Machine Learning Techniques. We are going to Problem statement is to detect the diseases of fruits using CNN.

Objective

Objective of our work is to collect, detect and classify the orange fruit diseases. Use machine learning algorithm and Image Processing to detect and classify the orange fruit disease. Compute the accuracy. Scope of our work is, automatically classify and detect the orange fruit diseases

Agriculture Overview

Agriculture is practice of cultivating plants. Agriculture was the key development within the rise of sedentary human civilization, where by farming of domesticated species created food surpluses that enabled people to live in cities. Plants were independently cultivated in a minimum of 11 regions of the planet. Industrial agriculture supported large-scale monoculture within the 12th century came to dominate agricultural output, though about 2 billion people still trusted subsistence agriculture. The major agricultural products are often broadly grouped into food and fiber. Food classes include grains, vegetables, fruits etc. Over 1/3rd of the world's workers is employed in agriculture, 2 nd only to the service sector, although in recent decades, the worldwide trend of a decreasing number of agricultural workers continues, especially in developing countries where small holding is being overtaken by industrial agriculture and mechanization that brings a massive crop yield increase. Plant breeding, agrochemicals like pesticides and fertilizers, and technological developments have sharply increased crop yields, but causing ecological and environmental damage. Environmental issues include contributions to heating, depletion of aquifers, deforestation, antibiotic resistance, and growth hormones in industrial meat production. Agriculture is explanation and sensitive to environmental degradation, like biodiversity loss, desertification, soil degradation and heating, all of which may cause decreases in crop yield. Genetically modified organisms are widely used, although some are banned in certain countries.

Fruit Disease

Fruit diseases are the disease that infects the fruit. Infection may occur in the mother tree itself but symptom expression may be in mother tree during harvesting or storage. Since fruits are the final product of the plant any infection in plant directly affects the income of farmer. Examples of fruit diseases are rot, greening, black spot, scab, mold, Anthracnose, Melanose, canker etc.

The period between the point of infection and point of symptom expression are known as latent period. To minimize the infection pre harvest spraying with fungicides in tree itself is important and also avoid mechanical injury during harvesting and handling and cold storage are important. For our approach we have decided to go with orange fruit and diseases selected for primary experiment is rot, scab, greening and canker.

Literature Review

- 1. Yudong Zhang and Lenan Wu et al.** adopted the model called split and merge algorithm it is based on quadree partition of an image. This method starts at the root of the tree that represents the whole image. If it is found inhomogeneous, then it is split into four son-squares (the splitting process), and so on so forth. Conversely, if four son-squares are homogeneous, they can be merged as several connected components (the merging process). The node in the tree is a segmented node. This process continues recursively until no further splits or merges are possible.
- 2. Sukhvir kaur et al.** they devised a rule based semi-automatic system using concepts of k-means and support vector machines to detect healthy leaves from diseased leaves. The best performing feature set for soya bean leaf disease detection.
- 3. Neha Mundokar et al.** they have used K-means clustering to perform image segmentation. The segmented images are labelled by maintaining a catalogue. Artificial Neural Network for pattern matching and disease classification. Diseases are categorized based on feature vectors, colour, morphology, texture.
- 4. V Puja Rahul Dar et al.** propose K-means clustering for image segmentation by using Otsu's method for setting the threshold. Thesholding is used to create gray-scale image from color images. They use Support Vector machines to classify the disease. The disadvantage in this proposal is that user to manually select the region of interest.
- 5. Mohammad Wannous et al.** they propose image processing using convolution neural network and use Transfer learning technique of machine learning for classification. They retrain the existing Googlenet Inception V3 model on a publicly available dataset. Tensorflow is used to retrain the Inception Model.
- 6. Akanksha Rastogi et al.** the image is processed to identify the plant using the features of the leaf using artificial neural network. The leaves are then subjected to disease classification using K-Means and artificial neural network.

Analysis Table

Sr. No	Title	Fruit/Disease/ Feature/ Dataset	Method	Accuracy / Precision
1	Orange Fruit Disease Classification using Deep Learning Approach (IJATCSE-Journal-2019)	Orange/ Brown Rot, Citrus Canker, Melanose/ color and texture	Classification: CNN	88.89% for Brown rot, 84.21% for Canker, 100% Melanose, 100% Healthy
2	Disease Classification and Grading of Orange using Machine Learning and Fuzzy Logic (IEEE-Conference-2018)	Orange/ Citrus Canker, Stubborn, Brown spot and Melanose/ color/ University of California Agriculture and Natural Resources	Collection of Sample: University of California Agriculture and Natural Resources Preprocessing: Image Enhancement and Lab Color Transformation Segmentation: K-means Feature Extraction: GLCM Classification: SVM	90%
3	A Deep Neural Network based disease detection scheme for Citrus fruits (IEEE-Conference-2020)	Citrus/ huanglongbing, Canker, Scab, and melanose/ color and texture/ Own Dataset	Acquisition: Own with Canon EOS 1300D DSLR Camera Preprocessing: Image rescaling, remove unwanted flickering, improve	89.10%

			contrast Data Augmentation:	
			rotation, width and height shift, rescaling, shear, zoom, horizontal and vertical shift, and brightness Classification: CNN	
4	An Optimal Weighted Segmentation with Hough Transform based Feature Extraction and Classification Model for Citrus Disease (IEEE- Conference-2020)	Citrus/ Blackspot, Canker, Greening, Healthy, Scab/ color, texture and shape/ Citrus Image Gallery Dataset	Preprocessing: BF Segmentation: OWS Feature extraction: HT Classification: RFANN	96.93%96.93%
5	An Effective Classification of Citrus Fruits Diseases using Adaptive Gamma Correction with Deep Learning Model (IJEAT-Journal-2019)	Citrus/ Blackspot, Canker, Greening, Healthy, Scab/ color and contrast/ Citrus Disease Image Gallery Dataset	Preprocessing: contrast enhancement (AGC) and noise removal (Bilateral Filtering) Segmentation: Otsu Method Feature extractor: Alex-Net model Classification: RF	97.29%

6	Automatic Citrus Fruit Disease Detection by Phenotyping using Machine Learning (IEEE- Conference-2019)	Citrus/ Anthracnose, Black spot, Canker, Citrus Scab, Melanose/ color and texture/ Kaggle	Classification: SVM and ANN Clustering: k- means	SVM: 93.12% ANN: 86.7% / SVM: 94.8% ANN: 86.7%
7	Classification of Fruit Diseases using Feed Forward Back Propagation Neural Network (IEEE-Conference-2020)	Any/ Bacterial and fungal diseases/ contrast/ gfar.net	Preprocessing: BF Segmentation: OWS Feature extraction: HT Classification: RFANN	Bacterial: 92% Fungal: 86% / Bacterial: 86.65% Fungal: 78.89% For 10 hidden Layers

Proposed Methodology

There are several steps to be followed in the system to predict the disease of the fruit or the leaf of the fruit plant those are basically starting from camera capture to training, segmentation, processing calculating weights and mapping with datasets and then predicting the disease that is present and also giving suggestion to overcome the problem.

Figure – 1 – Methodology Process

As mentioned before, the top-level use cases are here more appropriate to describe the user communication with the system. This is because they provide information not only about the system behavior, but also about the sequence of interactions that the farmers usually performs in order to achieve a goal. Once the farmer has some items scanned in his android phone, the next step is to navigate to the remedy page. Here the user can remove or modify his diseased part that has been scanned until the scan is clear to start the prediction process. Users can scan the same plant species multiple number of time. There, after entering all plant and required information, the system will confirm the disease and the system will display the remedies. The customer can choose an option between other scan and detailed analysis on the same problem. Once the farmer has some items scanned in his android phone, the next step is to navigate to the remedy page. Here the user can remove or modify his diseased part that has been scanned until the scan is clear to start the prediction process. Users can scan the same plant species multiple number of time. There, after entering all plant and required information, the system will confirm the disease and the system will display the remedies. The customer can choose an option between other scan and detailed analysis on the same problem.

Deep learning approach

Deep learning (DL) is a technique for implementing machine learning (ML) in artificial intelligence (AI). It was inspired by our understanding of the human brain which uses interconnections between neurons to learn hence the name Neural Networks (NN) [7]. Neural Networks have a variety of applications in computer vision such as image classification, speech recognition, face recognition and analysis of big of data. Increase of computational power and availability of more training data has caused deep learning networks to become very successful. For these reasons, researcher have been able to develop and train neural networks more efficiently.

Convolutional neural networks (CNN)

Convolutional neural networks are currently one of the most prominent algorithms for deep learning with image data. They have proven to deliver outstanding results in several applications most notably in image-related tasks. CNNs consist of multiple layers of connected neurons which can learn features automatically from datasets. CNNs use raw images as input to learn certain features and consist of an input layer, several hidden layers, and an output layer.

Figure 2:1 CNN Layers, source Stanford University [8].

Figure 2:1 shows a CNN where the red input layer consisting of an image is transformed into a 3D arrangement. The height and width of the hidden layer are the dimensions of the image and the depth consists of the three RGB channels.

Convolution Neural Network consists of various types of principle layers as shown in Figure 2:2. The main building blocks are as follows:

1. Convolutional layer
2. Rectified Linear Unit Layer
3. Pooling Layer
4. Fully Connected Layer

Figure 2:2: CNN architecture that classifies input images. Source Matlab [8]

Convolutional layer

The name “Convolutional Neural Network” indicates that the networks makes use of convolution operations. The primary purpose of this layer is to extract features from the input image. Figure 2:3 show an example of how convolution works in this layer. Consider an image of dimensions 5 x 5 whose pixel values can be either 0 or 1. A filter or kernel or feature detector of dimensions 3 x 3 is slid over the image and along the way we multiply the values in the filter with the original pixel values of the image.

Figure 2:3: Convolving an image with a filter, Source Stanford University [9]

After sliding the filter over the image, the result of the computation will be a 3 x 3 matrix called the activation map or feature map.

The convolution layer has following types of hyperparameters:

- Kernel or Filter size

A kernel or filter is used to extract features from an input image.

- Stride

The stride S denotes the number of pixels by which the filter window moves over the input matrix operation. It controls how the filter convolves for example, when the stride is 1 then we move the filters to 1 pixel at a time and so on.

- Padding

Padding involves symmetrically adding any number to the input image matrix to preserve the feature. The most common type of padding is zero padding. It works by adding zeroes to the input matrix to allow the size of the input to be adjusted to your requirement.

Figure 2:4 Zero Padding

Figure 2:4 shows an input matrix of 32 x 32 x 3 with two borders of zero padding applied around it to give us a 36 x 36 x 3 output matrix.

Rectified Linear Unit Layer

Rectified linear unit layer is an additional operation that is carried out after the convolutional layer to replace all negative pixel values in the feature map by zero and if it receives a positive value, the function will return the same positive value. It is graphically shown in Figure 2:5 and mathematically defined as below

$$F(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (2:1)$$

Its main purpose is to introduce nonlinearity in the network. This layer is made up of an activation function that takes the feature map from the convolutional layer and creates the activation map as its output.

Figure 2:5: Rectified Linear Unit

Pooling Layer

This layer is used to reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature map generated by the convolutional layer. Less spatial information means that you gain computational performance and less parameters reduces the chances of over fitting in a model. This makes the model more robust because of translation invariance in the position of the features in the input image

Figure 2:6: Max Pooling Operation [10]

Figure 2:6 show most common approach used in pooling is max pooling. The operation simply involves sliding a window over the feature map and taking the max value in the window.

Fully Connected Layer

After all the features have been detected from the combination of previous different layers, the fully connected layer is attached at the end of the network. It uses the detected features to classify the input images into various classes based on the training dataset. The output of the previous layers is flattened into a single vector of values. These values represent a probability that a certain feature belongs to a certain class. In the case of crop disease identification, the fully connected layer will then show you the probability that an input leaf image is affected by a which disease. An activation function is used at the end to get likelihood value between zero and one for each possible classification.

Possible challenges with deep learning

Overfitting and underfitting are the main challenges in deep learning. A good model is one that can generalize new and unseen data and not only test data. This is a measure of how well a model performs on unseen data[11]. Overfitting occurs when the model fits the training data too well or effectively memorizes the existing data as shown in Figure 2:7 to cause high variance[12].

Figure 2:7 Overfitting and underfitting

Underfitting occurs we have less data to train our model but quite high amount of features which causes it to not perform well even on the training set as shown in Figure 2:7. Therefore, there is need for a tradeoff between underfitting and overfitting.

Addressing Overfitting

To overcome the effects of overfitting and underfitting, techniques have been developed to improve the performance of the model. These techniques are called regularization techniques and as follows[13]:

1. Train with more data.

A larger training set helps your model to give you a better approximation and avoid underfitting.

2. Early stopping

In this method training data is split into validation set and test set then during training when we see that the performance on the validation set is getting worse compared to test set, we immediately stop the training on the model as show in Figure 2:8.

Figure 2:8 Early stopping technique, Tuan-Ho Le [14]

3. Dropout

This is the most frequently used regularization technique in the field of deep learning. Dropout involves ignoring neurons during the training phase of certain set of neurons which is chosen at random[14].

4. Data augmentation

This consists of the transformation of the geometry or intensity of the original images to make them seem like new images. The operations include rotation, zooming, mirroring, cropping, adjusting contrast and brightness values as well as simulating new backgrounds.

Hyperparameter tuning

In order to enhance the model performance there are a set of hyperparameters that need tuning. A hyperparameter can be any configurable variable that is a pre-determined before starting the training. Tuning these hyperparameters can effectively lead to a massive improvement in the accuracy of the model[15]. Below, we briefly survey the hyperparameters.

1. Learning rate

Learning rate controls how much to update the weight at the end of each batch in the optimization algorithm.

2. Number of epochs

Number of epochs is the number of times that the learning network will go through the entire training dataset. This number is increased until the validation and training error from the model has been sufficiently minimized.

3. Batch size

The entire dataset cannot be passed into the deep learning network all at once, so the dataset is divided into a number of batches or sets. The number of samples in each set is what is called a batch size.

4. Number of hidden layers

Adding more layers in a model has been proven to generally improve accuracy to a certain degree depending on the problem[16].

5. Weight initialization

It is necessary to that initial weights are set for the first feed forward pass. Two techniques are generally practiced initializing parameters which are zero initialization and random initialization.

6. Regularization

The appropriate regularization technique should be chosen to avoid overfitting in deep neural networks. As discussed in the previous section dropout is a preferable regularization method which involves ignoring certain neuron during the training phase.

Validation in deep learning

Model validation or testing is a process used to estimate the performance or accuracy of deep learning models[15]. This process is conducted after training has been completed to know how well the model will perform in real world. It is not a good practice to test the model on the same dataset used for training. So, to know the actual performance of the model, it should be tested on unseen dataset which is usually referred to as test set.

Types of validation methods

1. Holdout Validation

This is a simple approach in which the entire dataset is divided into three parts (training validation and testing dataset). The model is then trained on training data, fine-tuned using validation data and tested using the test set

Figure 2:9 Hold-out Validation

This method is mainly used when we only have one model to evaluate.

2. Leave-One-Out cross validation

In this method we keep only one instance of the data as a testing data and train the model on the rest of the data. This process is applied once for each data point. For example, if you have 500 instances of data it will iterate 500 times. One instance is allocated for testing and the rest for

training as shown in Figure 2:10.

Figure 2:10 Leave-One-Out cross validation

3. K-Fold cross Validation

K-fold cross validation is an improvement of the holdout validation method. The data set is divided into k number of subsets and the process is as follows:

1. Split the entire dataset randomly into k number of subsets or folds as shown in Figure 2:11
2. Train the model on (k-1) subsets of the dataset and then test the model on the kth subset
3. Repeat the process until each of the k-folds has been used as a test set
4. Take the average of your k subsets accuracy to get the model performance metric. This also called the cross-validation accuracy

Figure 2:11 K-Fold cross validation

The main advantage of this method is that It covers all the data instances and learns everything therefore the bias will be very low.

4. Stratified K-Fold cross Validation

This method is similar to k fold method, but the only difference is that it ensures that when we k fold the dataset each fold is a good representative of the whole dataset.

Figure 2:12 Stratified K-Fold cross Validation

An example of stratified k fold cross validation is shown in Figure 2:12 above.

5. Cross validation for Time series

This is the most sophisticated method of all the validation methods. It consists of a series of test subsets and the corresponding training subset contains only observations that occurred prior to the test set as shown in Figure 2:13.

Figure 2:13 Cross validation for Time series

Deep learning architectures

As discussed thus far, CNNs are based on three main layers which are convolution and pooling layer which act as feature extractors from the input image and fully connected layer which acts as a classifier. Several architectures have been developed in the past few years with varying number of layers and arrangements from one architecture to another. This section discusses multiple deep learning architectures notably LeNet, AlexNet, GoogleNet and ResNet.

LeNet

In 1994, one of the very first convolutional neural network architecture was proposed by Yann LeCun and was name LeNet5[17]. This architecture is made up of seven layers, which are three convolutional layers, two pooling layers and one fully connected layer followed by an output layer.

Figure 2:14:Architecture. Source: LeCun et al 1998 [17]

Its first use case was to automatically classify hand-written digits on bank cheques. LeNet-5 was able to achieve error rate below 1% on the MNIST dataset.

AlexNet

In 2012, Alex Krizhevsky and team released an architecture called AlexNet which was an advanced version of the LeNet architecture[18]. It consists of 5 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers.

Figure 2:15: AlexNet architecture Source: AlexNet 2012[18]

In that same year, AlexNet won the ImageNet competition by a large margin. It achieved this state-of-the-art performance in this competition because it used the novel ReLU activation, data augmentation, dropout to reduce overfitting and local response normalization.

GoogleNet or Inception v1

In 2014 Christian Szegedy from Google published a network known as GoogLeNet [19] which became the winner of the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Competition 2014, an image classification competition. It was able to outperform the other models because of the introduction of a concept called inception modules, so as a result the model runs very fast, has 12 times less parameters and more accurate. Also, it has lower power and memory use.

Figure 2:16 GoogleNet Architecture [20]

GoogleNet has 22 layers in total as show in Figure 2:16. and is also called Inception v1. In the same paper, Christian Szegedy and the team at Google also proposed several upgrades to the GoogleNet or Inception v1 model which increased accuracy and reduced computational complexity. This led to improved version namely Inception v2, Inception v3 and Inception v4.

VGGnet

VGGnet architecture was proposed by Simonyan and Zisserman from University of Oxford in 2014 [20]. This architecture was the 1st runner-up of the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Competition 2014 with a 7.3% error rate. VGGnet performed way better than AlexNet by replacing the large kernel filters in AlexNet with multiple 3x3 kernel sized filters.

Figure 2:17 VGGnet Architecture [21]

It has two versions VGG16 and VGG19. VGG16 is made up of 16 weight layers consisting of 13 convolutional layers and 3 dense layers for classification. VGG19 consists of a total of 16 convolution layers and 3 dense layers.

ResNet

In 2015 Microsoft published its own neural network known as ResNet [22]. ResNet was the winner of the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Competition 2015 with an error rate of 3.57%.

Figure 2:18 ResNet Architecture [23]

ResNet was designed to allow hundreds or thousands of convolutional layers. Other deep learning architectures drop off in effectiveness because of additional layers. This architecture can add many layers with strong performance. It was able to achieve high performance because of using different identity mappings building blocks which has several different paths of stacked identity layers with their outputs merged via addition.

Comparison

Table 2.1 Comparison table

Model	Year	Number of layers	Top-1/Top-5 Error %	Model Description
AlexNet	2012	8	41.00/18.00	5 conv + 3 fc Layers
Google	2013	22	29.81/10.04	21 conv + 1 fc Layers
VGG-16	2014	16	28.07/9.33	13 conv + 3 fc Layers
VGG-19	2014	19	27.30/9.00	16 conv + 3 fc Layers
Resnet-50	2015	50	22.85/6.71	49 conv + 1 fc Layers
Resnet-150	2015	152	21.43/3.57	151 conv + 1 fc Layers

Transfer Learning

In recent years, most applications of deep learning rely on transfer learning. Rarely do researchers train an entire deep learning network from ground up. This is because obtaining many images for a given class of diseases can be complicated especially in an agricultural context. A concept known as transfer learning is very useful in cases where you have insufficient data for a new domain to be implemented by a deep learning network.

Transfer learning is a machine learning method of using the knowledge of an already trained model to a different but related problem[24]. For example you might only have 600 images of a crop disease, but by leveraging on the knowledge of an existing model such as GoogleNet which has been trained on over million images, you can use the model as an either as an initialization or a feature extractor for the task of interest. Furthermore, training a deep learning network from scratch generally require multiple GPU's and the process is time-consuming process which can take up to 3 weeks[25]. This makes transfer learning an even easier and practical approach to consider.

There are different strategies and techniques for transfer learning usage patterns [26] as follows:

- **Classifier** - The pre-trained model is used directly to classify new images.
- **Standalone Feature Extractor** - The pre-trained model as an image preprocessor and relevant feature extractor.
- **Integrated Feature Extractor**: The pre-trained model is merged into a new model and layers added on top
- **Weight Initialization**: The pre-trained model is merged into a new model and the layers of the pre-trained model are trained together with the new model

Related work

Crop disease detection is still an active area of research. Several techniques have been implemented to detect crop diseases. The most common and simplest method used for detection of plant diseases is visual plant disease inspection by humans[27]. This traditional method is based on characteristic plant disease symptoms like blights, wilts, rots and lesions. Other techniques are performed by experts using different methods including visible light imaging, thermal imaging and chlorophyll fluorescence imaging[28]. Traditional methods are not reliable for detecting disease in crops because of lack of uniformity and the need for expertise and experience in the procedure. Also differentiating closely related strains may be difficult with traditional methods.

The science of crop disease diagnosis evolved from visual inspection to other better techniques which are based on the analysis of near-infrared reflectance on crop leaf[29]. They make use of highly sensitive sensors to measure reflectance, temperature, biomass and fluorescence of crops within different regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. The classification accuracies of these methods are very low. Although these methods are much more reliable and accurate than visual inspection, they have some limitations that block the effective use of these techniques for the detection of diseases in crops. The main limitations include deployment costs, availability, processing speed and real-time diagnostic capabilities.

Therefore, looking for less expensive, accurate and fast methods to automatically detect the diseases from the symptoms that appear on the plant leaf is of great significance. Techniques capable of overcoming these challenges are needed to allow for the automation of diseases identification in crops. Computer vision and image processing solutions offer great opportunities

for the automatic recognition of crop diseases[30]. These technologies play a big role in developing a monitoring tool for pests and diseases and for warning the communities of possible outbreaks.

Rothe, P. R and R. V. Kshirsagar [31] developed a system to identify and classify diseases in leaves using pattern recognition. The system was able to identify and classify three leaf diseases which are Alternaria, Bacterial leaf blight and Myrothecium with an accuracy of 85 percent. The technique involved image preprocessing and segmentation to isolate the leaf spots from the background. Hu's moments are then extracted as features for use in training of the adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system.

Computing enrichment on image using image edge is also another technique that has been proposed for crop disease identification specifically for [32]. The images undergo enrichment process first using image edge detection segmentation techniques followed by R, G, B color feature image segmentation which is carried out to get target disease spots. To recognize diseases, the image features such as boundary, shape, color and texture are extracted for the disease spots.

Another author also developed a system for diagnosis and classification of plant diseases using K-means clustering for image segmentation and neural network for classification[33]. The K-means clustering is used for classification of image pixels based on a set of features into K number of classes. K-Means clustering is mainly used to minimize the sum of squared distances between all points and the cluster center.

The algorithm for K –means Clustering follows the steps below:

1. Pick center of K cluster, either randomly or based on some heuristic.
2. Each pixel in the image is assigned to the cluster that minimizes the distance between the pixel and the cluster center.
3. Repeat computation of cluster centers by taking an average of all the pixels in the cluster.

Steps 2 and 3 are repeated until convergence is attained.

The efficiency of this algorithm is high but due to the need to determine the number of clusters

K, it brings certain difficulties for automated calculations.

Neural networks represent a huge breakthrough in pattern recognition and classification of images. Deep learning techniques have obtained significant success in several plant disease detection studies. Bouaziz B, Amara J and Algergawy [30] proposed a deep learning-based approach that automated the process of classifying banana leaves diseases. They made use of the LeNet architecture as a deep neural network to classify between healthy and diseased banana leaves. The researchers obtained encouraging results which proved that the proposed method can significantly be used to accurately detect leaf diseases with little computational effort.

Sladojevic S, Arsenovic M, Anderla A, Culibrk D and Stefanovic D [34] developed a new approach to recognize 13 types of crop diseases by using deep learning networks. The results from the experiments on the developed model achieved an average of 96.3% accuracy on separate class tests.

Fuentes A, Yoon S, Kim SC and Park DS[35] also developed a new approach but based on deep learning networks. They incorporated VGG net and Residual Network (ResNet) with three families of detectors which are Faster Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (Faster R- CNN), Region-based Fully Convolutional Network (R-FCN), and Single Shot Multibox Detector (SSD) to recognize nine different tomato diseases and pests. The model was trained on a large Tomato Diseases and Pests dataset and experimental results showed that the proposed system could effectively recognize nine different types of diseases and pests with high accuracy.

Fujita E, Kawasaki Y, Uga H, Kagiwada S and Iyatomi H[36]. developed a new practical cucumber disease detection system that used CNNs consists of an input layer, convolution layers, pooling, local response normalization operations and an output layer. The system based on CNNs attained an average of 82.3% accuracy under the 4-fold cross validation strategy.

Mohanty SP, Hughes DP and Salathé M [37] evaluated AlexNet[18] and GoogleNet[19] deep learning models applicability for for the classification problem. They analyzed the performance of deep learning architecture on the PlantVillage dataset by training the model from scratch in one case, and then by leveraging on already trained models using transfer learning. The overall accuracy obtained on this dataset by training from scratch was 85.53% and 99.34% in case of transfer learning. This approach also showed showing strong promise of the deep learning approach for similar prediction problems.

From the literature survey conducted in this section, we can conclude that convolutional neural networks (CNNs) has achieved impressive results in the field of image classification. Hence, in this dissertation, we will investigate the application of deep learning-based approach to detect diseases in crops. In the next sections, we will explain in detail the proposed method as applied to cop leaves.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter describes entire procedure of developing the model for crop disease recognition using deep learning. This includes the design specifics and the entire process in detail. The proposed solution and assumptions are thoroughly developed starting with dataset collection.

Research procedure

The following approach to the research was taken

Figure 3:1 Research procedure

Building of the Dataset

To train a deep learning network for our research problem, a dataset of diseased and healthy leaf images had to be acquired. The dataset was put together by downloading high quality diseased images on the internet from various sources and taking pictures of leaves using a mobile phone camera. Plants are affected by diseases caused by various pathogenic fungi, bacteria, and viruses and to damage by parasitic worms and physiological disturbances also classified as diseases. is threatened by different types of diseases, such as Alternaria macrospora and Bacterial blight among others. We have limited our study to only two main diseases because of time constraints. A brief description of the diseases of interest are as follows:

1. Alternaria leaf spot - *Alternaria macrospora*

Alternaria leaf spot is a common fungal disease in [38]. Main symptoms include small, circular, brown spots with purple margins varying in size from 1 to 10 mm in diameter as shown in Figure 3:2. The spots gradually turn grayish as the plant grows producing irregular dead spots areas on the leaf.

Figure 3:2 leaves affected by Alternaria leaf spot, Source: PlantVillage[34]

These symptoms are caused a fungus called *Alternaria macrospora* which survives on residues. This pathogen is an air-borne disease and can also be spread by water splashing on to healthy plants.

2. Bacterial blight

It is the most devastating crop disease. bacterial blight is caused by a bacterial called *Xanthomonas citri* subsp *malvacearum* which survives in infected crop debris and seeds. It starts out as angular, waxy and water-soaked leaf spot with a red to brown border on leaves, stems and bolls. As the plant grows, the spots gradually turn into brown necrotic areas as shown in Figure 3:3.

Figure 3:3 leaves affected by bacterial blight, Source: Clemson University[35]

If these diseases are left untreated, they will kill the plant. However, if they are diagnosed early, they can be treated, and the crop can be saved.

The third category of classification is healthy leaves to allow the model to tell the difference between a health and diseased leaf.

Dataset Annotation

After collecting the images various leaf images there is need to organize the images and associate a label to each image. It involves removing duplicated images and identifying diseases on the leaves and organizing the images into folders corresponding to the different classes (i.e. Bacterial

blight, Alternaria leaf spot and Healthy Leaves). This is a repetitive, time-consuming and necessary step in building up a dataset.

Dataset Division

For the purposes of training and testing the model, three separate datasets are required. In this process we are subdivided the dataset put together in the previous section into the following sets:

1. Training set

This is the actual set used to train the model to learn its hidden parameters such as weights and biases.

2. Validation set

The validation set is used to evaluate the model. This accomplished by manually fine-tuning model hyperparameters allowing the training process to be monitored and to detect overfitting. These include among others the learning rate, batch size and number of epochs.

3. Test set

This set is used when the training phase has been completed to evaluate the performance and accuracy of the final trained model.

Table 3.1 Dataset Organization

Share

View

> This PC > Desktop > msc com > Crop diagnosis > Dataset

Name

Test

Training

Validation

Dataset split ratio

Research on different separation ratios conducted, concluded that the ratio that gives better results is when about 80% of the images go for training and the remaining 20% is split equally between validation and testing[37][39].

Figure 3:4 Dataset structure

Image Processing

The next stage after building the dataset was preprocessing of the images. This process is very important in the deep learning pipeline to make sure the training data is standard before being feed into a model for training. For example, images must be resized to match the size required by the network, 227×227 for AlexNet, 224×224 for DenseNet, ResNet, and VGG, and 299×299 for Inception.

Data Augmentation

To enrich the dataset, several techniques were used to increase the number and diversity of the available images in the datasets. More augmented images increase the chance of the network to learn more features and to be able to accurately distinguish one class from the other [21]. The image transformations included resizing, cropping, flipping, rotations, color, contrast and brightness enhancements.

The augmentation options used for training are as follows:

- Rotation - Rotating an image randomly over various angle Brightness – Varying brightness on images to help the model to adapt to variation in lighting during training
- Zoom – Scaling input image by various factors
- Vertical/Horizontal Flip - Randomly flipping images vertically and horizontally.

Dataset composition

Table 3.2 : Dataset

Class	Original images	Original and augmented images	Training images	Validation images	Test images
Healthy leaves	256	3870	3096	387	387
Bacterial Blight	430	5982	4785	598	598
Alternaria	430	5982	4785	598	598

Neural Network Design

Having acquired the images and preprocessed them, the next step was to design a model and train it on those images.

Practical Considerations

In order to start developing the model, there are design choices that need to be taken into consideration. The main one being the architecture choice of the model. As discussed in the previous chapter it is now common practice to use a deep neural network that has been pretrained on a very large dataset and then leverage its knowledge as an initialization for our task of interest.

We discussed a number of architectures namely LeNet[17], AlexNet[18], GoogleNet or Inception v(1,2,3 and 4)[19], VGGnet[20] and ResNet[22]. In comparison to VGGnet and ResNet, Inception v3 have proven to use less computational power and its economical in terms of memory requirements especially considering that we will be using it on a mobile phone. For these reason Inception v3 was chosen as the architecture of choice for the purpose of this research. We use this architecture as a feature extractor but modify and fine tune it to support our disease classes.

Model design

We used the layers in the Inception v3 pre-trained model as a feature extraction component of our new model. The inception model was loaded without the classifier part of the model and added a new flatten layer, Dense layer, Dropout and Output layer altered for the requirements of our new dataset to predict the probability for 3 classes.

Figure 3:5: Deep neural network Figure 3:5 shows the block diagram design of our model. The block diagram was drawn using Deep Learning Studio[40].

Figure 3:5: Deep neural network

Visualizing output after every layer

Matplotlib was used to visualize the output of an image at every layer. For example, for the image in Figure 3:7, the output image can be visualized after each layer.

Convolutional layer 1 output

Figure 3:7 : Portion of a diseased cotton leaf

MaxPooling layer 1 output

Convolutional layer 2 output

Convert model to TensorFlow Lite

```
import tensorflow as tf

converter = tf.lite.TFLiteConverter.from_keras_model_file('crop.h5')
tfmodel = converter.convert()
open ("output_model.tflite" , "wb") .write(tfmodel)
```

Mobile application development

All code in this section was written in the Java programming language using Android Studio software[43].

Figure 3:8 Mobile application flowchart

Application layout

The layout was developed using Extensible Markup Language (XML). The main components of the layout are as follows:

- **Upload photo** - This is a button to allow the user to open the device gallery and select an image to classify.
- **Take photo** - This is a button to allow the user to open up the device camera and take a photograph of an image to be classified.

Figure 3:9: Application GUI layout

- **Image Display panel** – This panel is to display the photograph take or the image taken from the device gallery
- **Detect disease** – This button is used to initiate the classification process
- **Results** – This panel is used to display the inference results

Algorithm Flow

STEP 1: Setting Up android Application

Android application is designed with UI where the farmer can register himself and login with proper credentials and then login to the panel where he can capture and upload the picture for testing against the model file trained with 1000 of diseased dataset images with different fruits and categories.

STEP 2: Creating Model

The model is created with pre learned dataset which is appropriate for Tensor Flow framework to predict the disease of the test file.

STEP 3: Training and Testing

Tensor flow includes the details of the fruit and plant diseases and the model trained over the dataset, Training and testing sets are divided into a ratio of 10:1 respectively. The clustering algorithm is used to pre determine the tensor flow framework.

STEP 4: Testing Data

This is process of predicting the disease of the uploaded image from mobile capture it includes identifying and giving helpful remedies.

STEP 5: Optimization

The model is optimized by using the optimization techniques in the tensorflow such as model. Optimization, pruning, stemming. The display options are selected according the user from regional language or as set by user during login. The predicted information is displayed in this step and the remedies necessary is shown.

STEP 6: Prediction

This step displays the user the prediction of the current image taken by the farmer. It also displays the history and the current progress of the active diseases so that the user can track the health process. And also gives proper suggestions to over the issues.

Flow Chart of the Application

Figure – 2 – Flow Diagram

Resultants

The proposed model is been implemented in the computer device with 4GB RAM and 1TB hard disk. An android application is developed using android studio and run in the cell phones with 2GB RAM. The proposed system can identify the confidence level of the healthiness of leaf. It can also produce the kind of disease if attacked.

The results of the development of the plant disease identification using tensorflow over the traditional approaches are convenience to use, interactivity, large volume in prediction. As shown in the Figure 6, the number of days is given on x-axis and the yield of the crops or the health of plants mentioned on the y-axis. The Figure 3 displays the data of the machine learning system for the same values as used in traditional disease identification. The difference can be clearly observed. As sown in Figure3 the first blue line represents the data of traditional methods and the second red line represents use of tensorflow and machine learning data.

Figure – 3- Graph Machine Learning

Total number of samples taken are 1000 approx and there will be different type of images with different disease for different fruits with images has been taken and given for the training and then captured image will be tested against this 1000 trained data.

Table 1: Disease Analysis

Disease Name	Samples	Recognized	Missed	Rate of recognition
Anthracnose	150	143	7	91.3%
Bacterial Blight	150	148	2	98%
Apple Scab	150	138	12	89%
Die Back	150	144	6	92.09%
Crown Rot	150	147	3	97.90%
Cigar End Top	150	150	0	100%
Bacterial Canker	100	89	11	89.00%

Requirement Specifications

Software Requirements

- Operating System : Windows 8 above
- Programming Language : Java, Android API
- IDE : Android Studio

Hardware Requirement

- Processor : Intel ® i5
- Hard Disk : 100GB
- RAM : 8 GB
- Support : GPU CUDA

Conclusion

By this Methodology, we can assure with managing all sorts of identification of problems such as assembly line product identification, fruits or vegetables disease identification. It reduces the number of plants dying due to improper identification of disease. The main aim was to learn and design a machine learning application development inside an Android application. Providing flexibility of implementation of tensorflow framework inside any environment. This helped in creating our own android application which uses machine learning.

References

1. Savita N. Ghaiwat, Parul Arora, “Detectio and Classification of Plant Leaf Diseases Using Image processing Techniques: A Review” 3, 2014.
2. Savita N. Ghaiwat, Parul Arora presents and K-nearest neighbor (KNN) method for predicting the class of test example.
3. Renuka Rajendra Kajale, “Detection and Reorganization of Plant Leaf Disease Using Image Processing and Android O.S.” March-April 2015.
4. A.S.Deokar, Akshay Pophale, Swapnil Patil, Prajakta Nazarkar, Sukanya Mungase, Harshad Shetye, Tejas Rane, Tanmay Pawar, Prof. Anuradha Dandwate“ An Analysis of Methodologies For Leaf Disease Detection Techniques ” February 2016.
5. Yeh, R.A., et al.: Semantic image inpainting with deep generative models. In: CVPR. pp. 5485–5493 (2017).
6. Sukhvir Kaur, Shreelekha Pandey and Shivani Goel, “Semi-automatic leaf disease detection andclassification system for soybean culture”. IET Image Process., 2018, Vol. 12 Iss. 6, pp. 1038-1048
7. Neha Mundokar, Pratiksha Kale, Minal Bhalgat, Shalaka Koske, “Fruit Disease Detection Using Color Analysis and ANN with E-Nose”, Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research (IJIR) Vol-3, Issue-5, 2017 ISSN: 2454-1362,pp-1919-1923.

8. V Pooja ; Rahul Das ; V Kanchana, “Identification of plant leaf diseases using image processing techniques”, 2017 IEEE Technological Innovations in ICT for Agriculture and Rural Development (TIAR), April 2018
9. Boikobo Tlhobogang ; Muhammad Wannous, “Design of plant disease detection system: A transfer learning approach work in progress”, IEEE International Conference on Applied System Invention (ICASI), 2018,
10. AakankshaRastogi, Ritika Arora, and Shanu Sharma, proposed "Leaf Disease Detection and Grading using Computer Vision Technology & Fuzzy Logic"2nd International Conference on Signal Processing and Integrated Networks2015.
11. Rutu Gandhi ; Shubham Nimbalkar ; Nandita Yelamanchili ; Surabhi Ponkshe, “Plant disease detection using CNNs and GANs as an augmentative approach”, IEEE International Conference on Innovative Research and Development (ICIRD), 2018
12. Bhavini J. Samajpati ; Sheshang D. Degadwala, “Hybrid approach for apple fruit diseases detection and classification using random forest classifier”, International Conference on Communication and Signal Processing (ICCSP), 2019